

MEDICAL MALPRACTICE AND PATIENT RIGHTS IN PAKISTAN: GAPS IN LAW AND PRACTICE

Rameesa Shakeeb^{*1}, Dr. Tansif Ur Rehman², Dr. Aisha³

^{*1}Department of Law, Dadabhoy Institute of Higher Education, Pakistan

²Teaching Associate, Department of Sociology, University of Karachi, Pakistan; and Visiting Faculty, Department of Law, Dadabhoy Institute of Higher Education, Pakistan

³Women Medical Officer, Civil Hospital Naushahro Feroze

¹rameesas30@gmail.com, ²tansif@live.com, ³aishasolangi786@gmail.com

²<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5454-2150>

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Corresponding Author: *

Rameesa Shakeeb

Abstract

There are loopholes in law, regulation and enforcement that further dilute the rights of patients in Pakistan. There may be constitutional rights and laws that recognize the right to life and safe medical care, but there is no robust system of medical malpractice in the country to establish clear standards of care, liability and redress. Regulatory bodies such as the Pakistan Medical and Dental Council and provincial healthcare commissions are challenged by a lack of regulation, inconsistent compliance and limited investigative resources. This has either caused to block the patients from reporting the negligence or stopping them from getting the evidence or getting proper compensation. The lack of accountability is also because of lack of public understanding, long court cases and cultural deference to medical authority. In Pakistan, there is an urgent need to initiate a process of regulation and transparency as well as the registration of complaints and establishing a mechanism for accountability in order to get access of rights related to patients' care and over all health systems.

INTRODUCTION

Patient and medical malpractice is one of the major problems associated with health care system of Pakistan (Memon et al., 2023). Despite general principles on negligence regarding the Pakistan Penal Code, consumer law and tort law, the country lacks a dedicated medical malpractice statute (Saleem et al., 2023). It means that the patient would generally not have a course of redress in circumstances where they receive substandard care, are misdiagnosed or take advantage from a miscarriage of justice (Hussain et al., 2025). There is no single body that sets the standards or describes misconduct or prescribes an investigation process (Muttaqin & Amelia, 2024).

Disciplinary processes for the non-compliant practitioners by regulatory bodies like Pakistan Medical and Dental Council (PMDC) are slow, sparse and not commonly available to public in a transparent manner. Victims hesitate to place claims, owing to ignorance of the rights as victims, financial issues, or threat of retaliation against bringing about any decision (Akhtar et al., 2023; Qaiser et al., 2024). Moreover, the processes for obtaining informed consent are not available in Pakistan and the unequal power dynamics and lack of communication impede doctor-patient relationships (Rasheed, 2023). Public hospitals are typically underfunded and overworked and thus

more likely to make errors, and a private hospital might prioritize profit over openness (Sherin, 2023). The best ways to protect patients are improvement in legal aspects, professional responsibility and accountability, ethical medical practices and strengthening the patients through education about their rights (Qamar et al., 2023). This can be done only by the healthcare system, which can make sure of justice, safety, and trust.

Research Justification

The laws exist at the written level such as Pakistan Medical and Dental Council (PMDC) Ordinance and Consumer Protection laws in some provinces and also in constitutional provisions on life and dignity but there is a huge gap between the two, written laws and realization of the laws. Some of the complaints received point to systemic weaknesses, such as negligent treatment, lack of informed consent, misdiagnosis and poor complaint handling procedures that make patients vulnerable and have limited control over health care providers.

However, this study is crucial to follow the institutional, legal and socio-cultural factors causing such gaps. Pakistan's healthcare system is characterized by low levels of oversight and accountability and uneven distribution of accountability and implementation across the public and private sectors. Patients are unaware of their rights and, for most patients, financial, legal and administrative barriers prevent access to legal redress. The study will identify the areas where the law needs to be modified and enforced, through a systematic analysis of the current policies, cases of malpractices and regulatory frameworks. Lastly, the research will be informative to policy makers, health care providers and civil society and will strengthen patient protection, professional accountability and build a more trustworthy and just health care system.

Literature Review

Evidence on medical negligence and patients' rights from Pakistan suggests that the system has various disconnected dynamic changes, weak institutions, stagnant institutional frameworks and is not clearly defined in law (Akhtar et al.,

2023). The study concludes that Pakistan has no good medical malpractice law, a massive number of provisions under the Pakistani Penal Code can be applied against physicians, civil liability acts (torts), and consumer protection (Hussain et al., 2025). This molasses law is vague and lacks any form of transparency or clarity on standards of care, burdens of proofs or a mechanism for seeking redress. This leaves patient vague and health care practitioner hazy regarding what he must expect (Sherin, 2023).

The regulatory status of regulatory bodies like Pakistan Medical and Dental Council (PMDC) and its subsequent forms indicates vagueness in implementation, redundancy of regulations and lack of accountability mechanisms (Arimbi, 2025). Disciplinary actions in such institutions are generally dragged and sluggish due to bureaucratic impediments that inhibit patients from lodging complaints in the most effective manner (Memon et al., 2023). The institutional fragilization is causing an expansion of the gap between the expectations of the law and real clinical practice (Rasheed, 2023).

In addition, there are many documents that study systemic and socio-cultural barriers to patient rights (Sherin, 2023). Studies have always revealed that the level of awareness regarding informed consent, patient rights and inclusion of remedies is low (Saleem et al., 2023). In the same way, persistent social inequalities, illiteracy and economic dependence can also make people reluctant to question medical professionals about the expertise of health professionals (Arimbi, 2025). The instances of medical negligence hardly get reported; and if they do, the investigations seldom reveal conclusive outcomes even if there is sufficient evidence to substantiate such claims (Qamar et al., 2023).

Additionally, chronic structural issues in the health system include under-financing, poor clinical documentation processes, shortage of staff and overcrowding in hospitals (Qaiser et al., 2024). This puts one at risk of being misdiagnosed, errors while in the process, and negligent (Rasheed, 2023). That was a further backing to the fact that malpractice reform in Pakistan is quite limited in scope, design and implementation compared with

those areas of US or Canada which have this types/modes of high performance limits on medical tort compensation (Muttaqin & Amelia, 2024).

Historical Context of Medical Malpractice and Patient Rights in Pakistan

Medical malpractice and patients rights in Pakistan are an evolving phenomenon governed by conflicting forces: colonial traditions, long tradition of professionalism and growing awareness of the masses (Qamar et al., 2023). There were virtually few healthcare laws during the first phase of British colonial control. Instead of being a protectionist measure, the Medical Act of 1886 was a license law (Qaiser et al., 2024). Despite having these regulatory systems like State Clinical Practice Guidelines in Place since 1947, the medical responsibility has not improved over time and patient complaints seldom mention the medical bodies (Sherin 2023).

The debate on malpractice initiated in 1980s and 1990s after the urbanization, media attention and judicial activism (Memon et al., 2023). The tort law started to accept the plea of negligence, which raised the patients' rights to a higher level (Akhtar et al., 2023). The process of standards institutionalization started in the early 2000s when federal and provincial healthcare commissions were formed that provide processes of complaints, hospital inspection and service delivery (Muttaqin & Amelia, 2024). Despite this, there are still a number of issues that need to be dealt with, such as inconsistent enforcement and public awareness (Arimbi, 2025). However, the changes in professional autonomy have been gradual and there has been a shift towards greater accountability and recognition of patients as rights bearing persons (Saleem et al., 2023). This evolution is being witnessed in Pakistan today (Rasheed, 2023).

Theoretical Context of Medical Malpractice and Patient Rights in Pakistan

The medical malpractice and patient rights has a theoretical background based on the legal, ethical and professional principles that regulate the physician-patient relationship . Medical

malpractice is generally described as the breach of the duty of care, owed by a health care professional, to an individual which results in harm to the patient. The set of medical standards defines the duty of care and the standard of skill, knowledge and diligence reasonably required of medical practitioners. If such standards are breached by negligence, omission or mistake, then malpractice of claim may arise.

Patient rights are grounded in the principles of autonomy, justice, and human dignity, among others. The central right that underpins all these rights is that of informed consent . This means that clinicians should provide patients with sufficient information on diagnosis, the risks involved and the possible alternatives to treatment. This is to make sure that people are able to make informed and voluntary choices about their health. Confidentiality, privacy and the right to refuse treatment further support the autonomy of the patient and the preservation of his/her personal integrity.

For example, malpractice and patients' rights is an example of the balance between professional responsibility and personal empowerment. Adherence to patient rights would help to minimize risk of malpractice and also improve ethical care by improving transparency, communication and trust. All of these are part of the ways that systems of healthcare governance and legal safeguards are being formed today.

Laws Regarding Medical Malpractice and Patient Rights in Pakistan

In Pakistan, there is no separate law on medical malpractice and patients' rights. It is a combination of legal and regulatory provisions. Medical negligence can be a criminal, civil, consumer and professional issue and each has its own channels of responsibility and benefits. Under the criminal law, under the Pakistan Penal code, liability for rash or negligent act of a medical practitioner resulting in injury or death is provided. Such conduct, although not intentional, may be subject to criminal prosecution, especially in cases of gross deviation from accepted medical standards. These are statutory regulations that

prohibit any irresponsible act and raise the responsibility of practitioners.

In civil law a patient may sue for tort in negligence. The patient must prove: a duty of care existed; that this duty was breached; and that damage resulted. One of the reasons that could lead to contractual claims is if the private hospitals do not provide the services it promises the patients and the courts can award compensation and damages. The consumer laws also strengthen the rights of the patients by making healthcare as a service thus giving the people the right of redress in the consumer courts in case of failure of service delivery or in the event of poor healthcare.

The Pakistan Medical Commission and provincial health care commissions provide regulatory oversight. These organizations set standards of professionalism, investigate complaints and sanction professional misconduct or incompetence which may include fines, suspension or withdrawal of a licence. Patient rights are indeed a very basic component of this structure. Disclosure of risks, benefits and alternatives for individuals is their right and consent to any procedure means that. The constitutions promise the right to live and the right to dignity for all through safe, ethical and affordable healthcare. Besides, confidentiality, treatment and non-discrimination towards medical service will be guaranteed to the patients. Pakistan's multi-tiered legal system is a mix of criminal, civil, consumer and regulatory laws to help in maintaining accountability and safeguarding patient rights even though there is no single malpractice law in the country.

Challenges for Ending Medical Malpractice and Ensuring Patient Rights in Pakistan

Medical malpractice is a complex issue in Pakistan and it is informed by a number of legal, institutional, social and economic challenges. One of the main challenge is ineffective regulation and implementation policies in health care system. Since many hospitals, particularly those in the private sector, are willing to operate with little supervision, being careless is going to go unnoticed. Medical malpractice has its own legal system which takes a long time but because there

are no medical specialized courts and the rulings are different from time to time the victims of medical malpractice have a difficult time in the path of seeking justice. Fear of litigation and high cost of litigation also keep the patients silent especially the low income patients.

The second major health challenge is the lack of qualified medical personnel and inadequate medical training. The environment in which doctors work, and overwork, can lead to mistakes. At the same time, poor quality accountability controls and lack of ongoing professional development can make it difficult to maintain standards of care. The licensing, monitoring and disciplinary procedures for the negligent are also hampered by corruption within the licensing agencies, monitoring agencies and disciplinary bodies.

Public awareness is another issue of great concern. The rights of most patients are unknown to them and they do not know where to report any malpractice. Complaints are generally not from cultural issues such as blind faith in doctors and the culture of society not allowing to be in conflict with them. Further, the lack of EHR, lack of documentation and inadequate hospital management systems also make it difficult to prove negligence. Comprehensive reforms are necessary to guarantee the end of medical malpractice in Pakistan. Institutions need to be strengthened to help increase regulation and medical education needs to be improved, medical tribunals need to be independent and transparency needs to be increased. Other key components are patient protection laws at low cost, and public awareness campaigns. The solution to these linked problems is very little and insignificant patient safety and accountability in the healthcare system of Pakistan. Rebuilding trust, delivering quality care and saving lives of patients across rural areas of Pakistan requires partnerships between government, professional and civil society coupled with regular data collection and political efforts.

Opportunities for Ending Medical Malpractice and Ensuring Patient Rights in Pakistan

Medical malpractice is a serious issue in Pakistan, but there's not much talk about it. It is a threat to

safety of patients, trust of people and quality of healthcare. But there are various opportunities to be leveraged to stop malpractice and to ensure better rights of patients through legal, institutional and cultural reforms. A way that can be established to make it more accountable is to have a medical or dental council or other authorities that could have that responsibility. Encouraging carelessness by practitioners would be discouraged by open licensing and frequent testing of competencies and swift sanctions for faulty practice. It can also be strengthened by setting up independent oversight committees with the representation of the patients.

Second, of course, the legal system must change with regard to malpractice. Through a standard definition of negligence, a system of compensation and special medical tribunals, victims would have better access to justice, but in less time. There may also be legal aid available for patients, to even the playing field between patient and doctor. Thirdly, the role of hospital management and organization could play a big part in minimizing errors during the process. All health workers have to take part in a continuous professional development training programme, entitled ethics training.

Finally and most importantly, there's an opportunity to learn or patient empowerment. Informed consent, right to second opinion and complaints procedures can be covered by public education efforts, which can promote active participation in patient care. Legally hospitals are obligated to have on display charters of patients' rights in local language. At long last there's an opportunity to use technology. Transparency and traceability in the healthcare delivery system: Telemedicine audits and data-driven monitoring can help with transparency and traceability in health care delivery.

Medical malpractice can only be prevented in Pakistan by implementing multi level prevention strategy which includes regulation, legal reforms, and institutional reforms, patient empowerment and technological revolution. If patients are put at the center of the healthcare system and started accountable, then Pakistan can be a healthier and trustworthy healthcare system. All stakeholders including Government, professionals and civil

society and media must work cooperatively to ensure sustainability of reforms, ethics in practice, patient voice and equal change in the health care system both in urban and rural health care facilities across the country.

Discussion

There is a lot of disparity between the law and practice with respect to patient rights and medical malpractice in Pakistan. There is no common, centralized medical malpractice law; the Constitution of Pakistan enshrines the right to life and dignity and other health laws lay down standards of medical care. This often means that victims are left to hold no one accountable because policies are not linked, there is limited enforcement and victims know little about the remedies available. The lack of medical negligence courts also contributes to the slow pace of justice as the patient has no alternative but to take recourse to the councils or to file a civil case, neither of which can put forth any harsh sanctions. Furthermore, documentation and reporting of care as part of the culture of care is deficient in health care institutions. A lack of good medical records and awareness to patients is a challenge to transparency and investigation in many facilities. In addition, fear of retaliation, social pressure and financial issues are not conducive to filing complaints by the patients. These disparities in quality of service are also the result of little mandatory continuing education and risky control of licensing on the side of the practitioner. This has to be improved by having a more robust regulatory system, a more specific definition of malpractices in the law, special tribunals as well as educating patients on the rights of patients. They are the only ones who can be the lever that can help to implement the changes that are necessary to make healthcare accountable, safe and ethical in medical practice in general.

Conclusion

An instance of mismatch between law and practice in Pakistan is the rights of patient and medical malpractices. Although there is a constitutional and regulatory framework to promote the welfare

of the patients, it is weak and ineffective in its implementation and the end

The consequence is, if the person is negligent, he would be powerless to do anything, and there would be no remedy for him. There is also a lack of awareness, documentation and specialized courts of malpractice to seek justice. Also the irregular licensing and surveillance mechanism under which the medical workers work leads to the poor quality of services. The loopholes can only be closed by changing the law to clearly define what malpractice is and increase regulatory scrutiny and transparency of record keeping. Other relevant activities are public education activities to educate and empower patients to know and assert their rights. The government, medical institutions and civil society will have to engage via communication, and collaboration for good results. There are two important rules which make Pakistan's healthcare system more reliable and fair, accountability and patient safety, these are the reforms that are needed to benefit the country in the longer term.

Recommendations

Medical malpractice and patient rights are relatively undeveloped and still to be addressed issues in health care system of Pakistan. Patients should be treated in a proper, safe manner, but there is no clear law on medical negligence. The procedural hurdles, court fees and length of litigation as well as the Pakistan Penal Code and civil law provide very limited avenue for redress, with patients unlikely to go to court to seek justice for redressing their grievances. There are professional bodies such as Pakistan Medical and Dental Council that monitor professional conduct, but these are not enforced and accountability measures are not good. However, theoretically, there is no specific definition on the part of medical staff about informed consent, risk disclosure and even unified procedures, but in practice, informal guidelines are usually followed. This can cause errors, disputes, and even less people are aware of patients' rights in the community, allowing people to be exploited and/or treated poorly.

The rural and the disadvantaged ones are further disadvantaged given the absence of legal and

medical supports. There is a wide gap between the legislation and practice, requiring a complete overhaul of the medical negligence law including a more accurate definition of medical negligence, streamlined complaint processes, mandatory reporting and increased regulation. To fill this gap and to build trust and accountability towards the health care system in Pakistan, it was necessary to increase the awareness of health care providers and population about the patients' rights.

Research Limitations

Empirical data and documentation of medical malpractice and patient's rights is not available in Pakistan and there is no systematic way to keep records of such cases. In general, most of the cases of negligence are either not reported or are dealt with in a very informal way and thus they do not capture the extent of malpractice. Criminal cases are never tried and very few results of any case are published so there is no data to show the outcome of a case.

Smaller clinics and rural areas are where most malpractice occurs, but investigators have little access to these areas. Furthermore lack of ethics and cultural attitudes such as not encouraging patients to participate in research, or report bad experiences discourage patients. The access of researchers to sensitive medical records and the absence of institutional assistance and effective sanctions is even an issue. So the research is not well coordinated but through the interpretative evidence or in some cases media coverage; not through a detailed research. The inadequate data gathering and openness of reporting systems and institutional support have resulted in weak academic knowledge and have curtailed opportunities for sound proposals for reform and policy development. There should be more openness in accountability and control!

Research Implications

The study results could significantly influence medical practice, policy and legal changes as well as medical malpractice and patient rights related issues in Pakistan. Gaps in the law and its application can result in a more specific definition of legal aspects such as negligence, patient consent

and avenues for redress. Using empirical research on the systematic vulnerabilities of the system, regulators can be informed and can strengthen the accountability systems and professional behavior unified. By knowing the trend and barriers to malpractice and injustice, the policy makers can focus on creating awareness campaigns for the population particularly in rural and marginalised areas.

The studies can also identify the differences in the access to legal redress, and make verification processes for complaints cheaper and quicker. Also, the law, medicine and ethics are interdisciplinary courses which may lead to greater educational opportunities for health care practitioners in the fields of patient's rights, and risk management. Finally, systematic research will give the evidence-based information, which will help in linking the statutory provision and its application, in turn resulting in patient safety, patient confidence and patient equity in the Pakistani healthcare system.

Future Research Directions

Future studies on the topic of medical malpractice and patient rights need to concentrate on different aspects of the issue in order to improve the quality of healthcare and protection of patients in Pakistan. First, an extensive data collection would be necessary for getting the precise/accurate prevalence, the types of malpractice and the causes in the public and private healthcare systems including the rural and underserved communities. Second, the research on patients should include the level of awareness, experience and barriers to obtaining remedies, which will inform the development of effective education programs and advocacy.

Research can also be done to know if the current legal and regulatory processes are effective or not, what are the gaps in them and what can be put in place to make them more accountable and faster to process complaints. Thirdly, research into professional training and hospital management could offer lessons on how to avoid mistakes, through ongoing training, protocols and better infrastructure. Finally, the comparative study with other countries can give information about best

practices. In future research, the evidence-based policy will be based on the greater rights of the patients and decrease in medical malpractice in Pakistan in general.

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